

Diphenylthiovioluric Acid as a Sensitive and Selective Reagent for Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium (II)

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Diphenylthiovioluric acid has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II). The 1 : 2 (metal - ligand) complex exhibits maximum absorption at 425 nm. The system obeys Beer's law upto 4.96 ppm of Pd with sensitivity of 0.0035 $\mu\text{g Pd/cm}^2$ for an absorbance of 0.001. The method has been proposed for the estimation of 7 - 35 $\mu\text{g Pd}$ over the pH range 1.0 - 3.5. The effect of foreign ions has been studied and the determination has been carried out in synthetic mixtures.

SOME of the important reagents used for the determination of palladium are *p*-nitrosodimethylamine¹, *p*-nitrosodiphenylamine², 5-amino-2-benzimidazolethiol¹, arsenazo(III)³, 8-mercaptoquinoline¹, tropolone⁴, dimethylglyoxime¹, methylglyoxime and salicylaldehyde^{1,5}. The purpose of the present investigation was to develop a new spectrophotometric method for the determination of palladium. In the present case, diphenylthiovioluric acid (DPHTVA) is more sensitive than methylglyoxime, salicylaldehyde and 8-mercaptoquinoline. The reagent compares favourably with the other methods from the point of view of selectivity which has been further increased by introducing suitable modifications in the procedure. The colour remains stable for more than 48 h under the studied conditions. Most of the associated base metals, platinum metals and common ions do not interfere.

Experimental

A stock solution of palladium was prepared by dissolving palladium dichloride (Johnson-Mathey) in dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardised gravimetrically by precipitation with dimethylglyoxime. Diphenylthiovioluric acid was prepared by the reported method⁶. The solution of the reagent was prepared in acetone. Chloroform was purified by shaking with dilute solution of ascorbic acid and distillation. All other solutions were prepared with A.R. grade chemicals in double-distilled water.

A Metrohm E-350 pH meter was used for pH measurements. All absorbance measurements were carried out with a Upicam SP 600 spectrophotometer using 10 mm matched glass absorption cells.

Procedure : To an aliquot of solution containing 7 - 35 μg of palladium, ten times molar excess of

the reagent in acetone was added and the pH adjusted to 1.0 - 3.5 with sodium acetate and hydrochloric acid. The volume of the solution was raised to approximately 10 ml with water and then heated on a water-bath to evaporate acetone. The solution was then cooled and chloroform (10 ml) added and shaken for 5 min. The separated chloroform layer was centrifuged to remove water droplets, the absorbance measured at 425 nm against a reagent blank, and the amount of palladium evaluated from a calibration graph.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of foreign ions was studied in the determination of 3.55 ppm of palladium(II). It was found that iodide, fluoride and thiosulphate interfere in the determination. The tolerance limits (in parentheses, ppm) of various anions and cations are as follows : bromide (250), borate (1000), citrate, tartrate, nitrate, pyrophosphate or phosphate (2000), nitrite (1200), oxalate (250), Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} or Sr^{II} (1000), Pb^{II} (100), Sn^{II} (10), Sb^{III} (100), Mg^{II} (500), Cd^{II} (1000), Al^{III} (100), Ag^I (20), Bi^{III} or As^{III} (100), Se^I (20), Te^{IV} (40), Tl^I (100), Hg^{II} (10), Ce^{III} (20), W^{IV} (500), V^V (250), Be^{II} (1000), Ga^{III} or La^{III} (200), Th^{IV} (500), U^{VI} or Mn^{II} (1000), Zn^{II} (1500), Cu^{II} (150), Ni^{II} or Co^{II} (200), Fe^{II} (20), Fe^{III} (120), Au^{III} (2), Rh^{III} (20), Ru^{III} (20, cit), Os^{VIII} or Ir^{III} (20) and Pt^{IV} (10).

Determination of palladium in synthetic mixtures : Palladium was determined in synthetic mixtures and the results are summarised in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

When an acetone solution of DPHTVA is added to a solution of palladium(II), a yellow precipitate appears at room temperature. The precipitate was found to be soluble in chloroform and carbon tetrachloride giving intensely coloured solutions. The

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TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Pd IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Pd taken = 3.55 ppm, pH = 1.75

Other ions present (ppm)					Pd found (ppm)	Error %
I	II	III	IV	V		
PtIV (5)	IrIII (5)	RhIII (5)	CoII (20)	NiII (20)	3.54	-0.28
PtIV (10)	IrIII (10)	CoII (50)	NiII (50)	FeII (20)	3.56	+0.28
PtIV (10)	IrIII (10)	CoII (50)	FeIII (20)	CuII (50)	3.60	+1.41
PtIV (10)	RhIII (10)	OsVII (10)	CoII (50)	—	3.55	+0.00
RhIII (10)	OsVIII (10)	CuII (50)	FeII (50)	—	3.56	+0.28
RuIII (10)	RhIII (10)	FeIV (10)	FeIII (10)	CuII (50)	3.53	+0.56
Tart-(500) rate RuIII (10)	RhIII (10)	PtIV (10)	AuIII (0.5)	—	3.55	0.00
Tart-(500) rate FeIII (20)	FeII (20)	CoII (50)	NiII (50)	CuII (50)	3.54	-0.28

chelate, extracted in chloroform, is quite stable and no change in absorbance was noticed upto 48 h.

Absorption spectra and effect of pH: The maximum absorption of the complexes at different pH values were plotted and it was found that all the curves are similar and exhibit maximum absorption at 425 nm indicating the formation of only one complex under the conditions. Subsequent studies have been carried out at 425 nm using the corresponding reagent blanks because the ligand also absorbs (120D) at this wavelength. Measurement of absorbances showed that the pH range within which maximum and constant absorbance is exhibited lies between 1.0 and 3.5. Above pH 6.0, the absorbance is insignificant. Subsequent work was carried out at pH 1.75.

Absorbance deviations: Measured under the experimental conditions, eight solutions each containing 18 ppm of Pd gave a relative average deviation of $\pm 0.4\%$ with standard deviation of 0.0034.

Stoichiometry of complex: The molar composition was ascertained by the application of mole-ratio method⁸ and Job's method^{9,10} of continuous variations. Both the methods indicated the formation of a 1:2 (Pd-DPHTVA) complex in the system.

Instability constant of complex: The values of E_m (maximum absorbance in presence of an excess of the reagent) and E_s (absorbance when the reagent is present in stoichiometric ratio) were obtained from the plots of reagent concentration. The value of α ($= E_m - E_s / E_m$) is 0.30 and that of instability constant is 2.9×10^{-10} at pH 1.75.

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